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**STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS ON THE USE OF
TRANSLANGUAGING IN EFL CLASSROOM**

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Abstract

Translanguaging plays a pivotal role in multilingual classrooms. In most of the cases Pakistani students tend to switch languages during teaching and learning process. The researcher explored the perceptions of students on the use of translanguaging in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms in Baluchistan. The current study is based on the Translanguaging Theory, proposed by Gracia and Li wei (2014), which presents a comprehensive overview on multilingual practices in the pedagogical context. This theory unveils the strategical linguistic usage by teachers and students in order to teach and understand the difficult concepts, classroom participation and to deduce the meaning by analyzing the context. The sample of the present study included 400 students participants (251 male and 149 female) from two districts of Baluchistan. A survey was conducted through 50 questionnaires for students' responses. The findings of the present research reveals that the purposeful use of translanguaging for learning English in the Pakistani context is an effective strategy for students. Further, this study will have important implications for representatives, practitioners, and researchers in the field of English linguistic and literature.

Keywords: *Translanguaging, Students, Male, Female, questionnaires, English as foreign Language (EFL), Urdu*

INTRODUCTION

The translanguaging phenomenon is increasingly recognized as an effective strategy in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms, as it enable learners to use their first language in order to enhance the understanding of pedagogical content. Traditionally, EFL instructions have been promoted the exclusive usage of target language to ensure maximal exposure. However, recent studies have challenged this concept by emphasizing the pedagogical importance of translanguaging. It allows learners to utilize their linguistic repertoire for better understanding of comprehension.

According to Baker (2001), trasnlanguaging serves four purposes in EFL classrooms. At the initial stage, it assists students in understanding the lesson. Secondly, it works to foster a positive collaboration among students; for instance students with high English proficiency can assist those with lower proficiency. Thirdly, it contributes to learners' language skills development especially in target language. Finally, translanguaging enables parents to support their children's acquisition of target language by guiding them through the first language. The current study aims at having an insight to elucidate the perceptions of learners regarding the usage of translanguaging at undergraduate level in two districts of Baluchistan.

Language plays an important role in impacting the society. People living in a same society may have ability to speak more than two languages; termed as multilingualism (Webster, 1961). It is a multidimensional study connected with different areas of sociolinguistics and applied linguistics. While living in a multilingual society majority of people tend to exchange words from one language to another language during their conversation (Milroy & Gordon, 2003). As a result of globalization language now a days became an intertwining phenomenon, which refers to the emerging term translanguaging, commonly referred as a communicative practice (Wei Li, 2018). In the pedagogical

context, practice of translanguaging facilitates communicative competence, which assists in the development of language and shaping the mediating language usage (Canagarajah, 2018).

According to Jamshidi and Navehebraim (2013), translanguaging is a technique, usually bilingual or multilingual speakers in order to achieve better understanding within the same discourse. Over the past decades, the concept of translanguaging has been widely used across a variety of multilingual contexts and also scholars have engaged in its conceptualization in educational context (Garcia & Li Wei, 2018).

A case study conducted by Paramesvaran and Lim (2018), compared the beliefs of teachers and learners in order to find out the use of translanguaging in classrooms of learning English as a Foreign Language. Sample of the study consisted of a multilingual teacher and three multilingual students of primary level. The data collected through observation and group interview from the participants. Findings of the study revealed that code switching reinforced the learning and understanding of students. It also encourages the class participation of students. Findings of the data collated from students revealed that code switching facilitate them when teachers practiced it for explaining the lesson

Statement of the problem

Learning of English as a Foreign Language has been immensely emphasized by the government in Pakistan. As per HEC, the policy regarding the medium of instruction at the undergraduate level should be English. Regardless of these policies, translanguaging is an extensive practice across Pakistan that has various impacts on teaching and learning process. It is essential to explore the perceptions of students regarding translanguaging in classrooms. Additionally, ample of researches conducted in International and Pakistani context. However, the perspective of students, region of district Sibi and Kachi, Balochistan, in this regard has been ignored. The current study differs from existing researches because it will carry out in a region where students belong to multilingual and diverse cultural background.

Objective of the study

● To examine the learners' perceptions regarding the usage of translanguaging in the EFL classroom in two districts of Baluchistan i.e. Sibi and Kachi. .

Research Questions

1. What are the perceptions of students regarding the usage of translanguaging in EFL classrooms.

Significance of the study

The present study is significant as it provides an empirical insights into the use of translanguaging in English as a foreign language (EFL) classrooms. Its findings can assist policymakers and educational authorities-particularly the Higher Education Commission (HEC) of Pakistan, in formulating context-sensitive language policies that ensure an effective English teaching and learning process. Moreover, the research is also important for curriculum designers and material developers, as it renders guidance to integrate translanguaging into diverse teaching practices to improve learners' engagement. Additionally, the current research supports learners by promoting inclusive teaching practices that lower learning anxiety. Finally, the study enriches existing literature and serves as a foundation for future studies on translanguaging in various EFL contexts.

Breakdown by Institution can be seen below

1. Govt. Boys Degree College Mach: 20 participants
2. Govt. Girls Inter College Mach: 12 participants
3. Govt. Boys Govt Girls Inter College Dhadari: 13 participants
4. Inter College Dhadar: 26 participants
5. Govt. Boys Inter College Mathri: 12 participants

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6. Govt. Boys Inter College Bhag: 23 participants
7. Govt. Boys Degree College Sibi: 86 participants
8. Govt. Girls Degree College Sibi: 50 participants
9. Mir Chakar Khan Rind University Sibi: 158 participants

Literature Review

Defining terminology

According to Grosjean (2010), individuals who use two or more languages in their everyday lives across various experiences are known as multilinguals. In contrast, individuals who live in monolingual society typically rely on one language in daily use but then suddenly shift their language if they see bilingual or multilingual people around them. It indeed creates a sociable learning environment and simplify the understanding of complex concepts. In the recent researches mutiplr terms have been used in order the phemenon of bilingual practices, such as code switching, code mixing, translanguaging or translingualism (Moody et al., 2019). The idea of translanguaging was first coined by Cen Williams in 1996 as a Welsh word “trawsieithu” that referred to the structured switching between Welsh and English language in pedagogical context. Gradually, the notion evolved into a broader and multifaceted paradigm, facilitating not only in educational contexts but also in sociolinguistic discourse for both personal and professional communication (Yuvayapan, 2019).

Translanguaging

Translanguaging is a natural linguistic process where individual switches between two or more languages during conversation. It is not a static or artificial process, but a real change in language use that is directly influenced by the social and cultural environment around them. Initially, it was considered a sign of poor language skills, but gradually researchers recognized its psychological, social, and educational complexities and usefulness (Wheeler, 2006).

Further, another scholar Haliza (2013), believes that translanguaging is a natural According to Fachriyah (2017), translanguaging has several meanings that show its impact in educational, societal, psychological, and cultural fields. In the enlightening field, the descriptive function of translanguaging helps students understand complex concepts.

Overall, translanguaging is a complex linguistic, social, and cultural process with multiple functions. Furthermore, Its appropriate use in the educational field can make the lessons and learning process more effective. However, it necessitates proper planning, teacher training, and clear course of action. translanguaging should not be well-thought-out a final solution to educational problems, but rather a useful teaching tool. If used wisely and fittingly, it can prove to be a powerful and effective teaching tool in the educational field (Shavkatovna, 2024).

International research on translanguaging

The use of translanguaging should always be deliberate and purposeful. According to Penelope (1998), If it is used comprehensively and chaotically, it can also hinder the language learning process whereas, if translanguaging is used with proper planning,

better teacher working out, and clear guidelines, it can be a powerful and effective coaching tool in the educational field (Chloros, 1998). A research conducted in Malta at secondary level extracted three main purposes: "to construct knowledge in the curriculum, to relate to monolingual English texts, and to build interpersonal relationships" (Grima, 2013).

English language teachers and students in Malaysia use translanguaging re-currently in regular classrooms. The aim of a study was to explore the learners' attitudes towards the functions of translanguaging by English language teachers at tertiary level. The population of the study consisted of forty-five diploma students. The data collection apparatus was questionnaires. The results of the study revealed that ESL students prefer translanguaging, according to them translanguaging helps learners to understand ESL. The results of the study also show that translanguaging in the classroom during the teaching process helps learners to understand their lessons effectively and they become more proficient in speaking English (Omar, 2011).

It is a conventional fact that globalization has turned the world into a global village. It has fashioned a multicultural environment in every junction of the world. As a result, people from different cultural and linguistic backgrounds have come into contact with each other. This has correspondingly affected the educational environment of different countries in terms of language usage. Similarly, translanguaging in the classroom is a common situation in many bilingual classes (Hasan, 2015).

Translanguaging in the Pakistani Context

Pakistan is a country with a rich folklore of linguistic assortment. According to researchers, about 77 languages are spoken in different regions of Pakistan. This linguistic diversity has created a unique bilingual and multilingual environment in the country. The present study examines another bilingual context of Pakistan, to explore how people communicate through translanguaging between a local language (Urdu) and a global language (English). Findings reveal that people usually communicate by switching between Urdu and English in order to facilitate the communication process. (Younas et al., 2020).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Institution’s Information

Data for the present research was gathered from the colleges and university of public sector of Baluchistan (District Sibi and Kachi)

Research Design

In fact, the current study uses a quantitative design to investigate students’ perceptions towards the use of translanguaging in EFL classrooms. The use of a structured questionnaire ensured standardization of responses and reduced researcher bias.

Table 1. Research Design

Component	Description
Research Design	Exploratory Quantitative Design
Purpose	Investigate the perceptions of student’s towards the use of translanguaging in EFL classrooms
Nature of Study	Exploratory – to examine unexplored dimensions of bilingual practices in Pakistani higher education
Approach	Quantitative – to measure responses numerically for statistical analysis of trends, relations and patterns
Research Method	Survey Method
Data Collection Tool	Structured Questionnaire
Rationale for Method	Easy collection of data from a large sample within a short time; ensures standardization and minimizes researcher bias
Target Population	Students and Teachers in Pakistani Higher Education Institutions
Data Type	Numerical (Quantitative) Data

Table. No. 1, Research Design: Sources made by Author.

3.6 Population of the Study

Distribution of Sample Population (n = 434)

S. No	Institution Name	Population	Sample Allocation (Student)
1	Govt Boys Degree College Mach	382	20
2	Govt Girls Inter College Mach	166	12
3	Govt Boys Inter College Dhadar	351	13
4	Govt Girls Inter College Dhadar	164	26
5	Govt Boys Inter College Mithri	151	12
6	Govt Boys Inter College Bhag	301	23
7	Govt Boys Degree College Sibi	1,404	86
8	Govt Girls Degree College Sibi	847	50
9	Mir Chakar Khan Rind University Sibi	2,214	158
Total		5,980	400

Table. Number 3. Distribution of Sample Population (n = 400), made by researcher.

3.10 Data Collection Instrument

The study used a structured questionnaire to collect data, which we actually got from a previous study (Ahsan, 2016). This questionnaire was specifically designed to find out how students feel and what their opinions are about the use of translanguaging in EFL classrooms.

The questionnaire was divided into two parts:

1. **Part A:** Personal information — such as gender, age, educational level, institution. This information assistance us comprehend the participants response in a better way.
2. **Part B:** Opinions and State of mind — this portion of my research contained 50 opinion-seeking statements. The reality to the fact is that in front of each proclamation, all the 400 participants were asked to express their opinion, feeling and emotions on the following scale.

Table Number: 5 Five-point scale:

Rating	Label	Description
1	Strongly Disagree	Completely different from my feelings or beliefs
2	Disagree	Generally don't agree; my thoughts don't match it
3	Unsure	Uncertain; my feelings are not clear
4	Agree	Generally agree; aligns with my feelings
5	Strongly Agree	Completely in line with my feelings and beliefs

This method helps us to understand the nuances and feelings our participants have about the topic.

ongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree.

Researcher's opinion poll covered the Perceptions of students on switching between different languages in EFL classrooms

3.15 Data Analysis and Interpretation

This part of our research involved the analysis and interpretation of all the data we collected through our questionnaires. We analyzed this valuable data using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.

3.15.1 Descriptive Statistics

We first calculated the following indicators to understand the general situation of the data:

er and Percentagevide an overall overview of the responses to each item;		
		etermine the general trend of participants' responses
	ard Deviation	imate the degree of variability in the responses

DATA ANALYSIS

On the basis of quantitative data collected through questionnaires the results clearly show that students consider their L1 as an important support for learning a difficult language like English. It serves as a facilitating agent in order to understand the complex grammar rules, idioms and proverbs, or those difficult words whose meanings are not clear or difficult to understand — when the teacher explains difficult concepts in Urdu or in L1, the matter immediately becomes clear. This gives us the advantage that it becomes easier to relate the rules and words of English to our own language. As if a puzzle has been solved.

In addition, when the teacher explains a complex lesson or idea in our own language, it is not limited to just words or rules, but the purpose and main idea of the entire lesson is revealed to us. It seems as if the path has been cleared and there are no obstacles in the way of understanding.

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In addition to the cognitive benefits, the data also highlight the profound emotional benefits of using the L1 (L1). Learners reported that when Urdu is used strategically, they feel significantly more motivated (Items 35-37, mean=3.78-3.82), motivated (Item 39, mean=3.82), relaxed (Item 33, mean=3.72). Most importantly, they strongly believe that the L1 or Urdu language “reduces emotional barriers” to learning a second language (Item 26, mean=3.85) and creates a “positive emotional environment” (Item 24, mean=3.82). This suggests that using the L1 reduces the “emotional filter,” which is a psychological barrier that can hinder language learning. This creates a classroom environment where students feel safe, ready to try new experiences and actively participate

Finally, students consider their L1 or Urdu as a useful medium for understanding classroom procedures and instructions. They strongly insist that the use of Urdu is essential for understanding basic instructions (Item 38, mean=3.88), classroom rules (Item 43, mean=3.90), and exam-related details (Item 14, mean=3.84). This makes the routine tasks of the class easier and clearer, thus saving more valuable time for learning English.

4.3 Demographic Profile of Respondents

While analysing the demographic information I got respondents from various languages i.e. Urdu, Balochi, Brahvi, Sindhi, Pashto, and Punjabi.

I do think that the linguistic diversity further broadens the scope of my research. This shows that for many respondents Urdu is not even a deeply rooted L1, but a 'lingua franca', a medium that connects them with each other. From the argument, it can be said how complicated the voyage of learning English becomes for them. First, they think in their home dialect, which is a great concern for many, then they switch over to Urdu, which never happens in the western world, and then they have to take on a new language, English. This is a new case, which requires deep understanding of the issues; therefore, if we fall behind in the education field, we sometimes force our children to bite off more than they can chew. This study will try to understand how the students also think of this dilemma.

In the first section of my research, I have made a table and graphs below where you can see the breakdown. Out of the 400 students, their responses reflect a wide range of linguistic backgrounds, gender balance, and years of experience in learning a foreign language. In fact, these institutions includes, Govt Boys Degree College Mach, Govt Girls Inter College Mach, Govt Boys Inter College Dhadar, Govt Boys Inter College Mithri, Govt Boys Inter College Bhag, Govt Boys Degree College Sibi, Govt Girls Degree College Sibi, Elementary College Sibi, and Mir Chakar Khan Rind University Sibi — two hundred males and two hundred females. When it comes to L1, 32.8% of students spoke Balochi, 19.2% spoke Sindhi, 11.5% spoke Pashto, 5.8% spoke Urdu, while 30.7% either spoke other languages or did not specify. Regarding their experience with learning a foreign language, 36.5% had been learning for 1 to 5 years, whereas a larger portion—63.5%—had been learning for six years or more.

4.4 Analysis Guided by Research Questionnaires

This is one of the most important facts to say — my questionnaire had 50 questions for the 400 students. Behind each question was a thought, a deep purpose, to reach those special places in the minds of the students where their true feelings about this conflict between the L1 and English are stored. It has been recorded that a large number of students seem to be clearly in favor of using Urdu or L1 in English classes. This is not a stubbornness, but a well-thought-out view. They see Urdu as a support, not an obstacle. When it comes to understanding, when it comes to unraveling complex topics, or when the class environment seems so stressful that there is hesitation in speaking. It is a means of facilitating their learning process.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Students (N=400)

<i>Demographic Variable</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Gender	Male	251	63.0%
	Female	149	37.0%
L1	Balochi	131	32.8%
	Sindhi	77	19.2%
	Pashto	46	11.5%
	Urdu	23	5.8%
	Other/Not Specified	123	30.7%
Years of Learning a Foreign Language	5-10 years	146	36.5%
	10 years and above	254	63.5%

Indeed, the table and figure 1 above clearly illustrate that this data presents a detailed diagram of a multi-layered landscape.

1. This is not just an unresponsive database, but a gathering of four hundred distinct perceptions of students, in fact, each with their own cultural and linguistic identity that create a common atmosphere in the English classroom which I consider as beauty of the classrooms.
2. The proportion of this group consist of 251 male and 149 female students. It means that the opinions we receive will not be a reflection of one gender. The ratio of representation is almost equal on the basis of total strength and guarantees that our results will be shaped by the shared experiences of all students. In fact, the real soul of this entire map is the fascinating diversity of its languages. The column titled “Mother Language” is not just a statistic, but a symphony of different cultures and regions all contained in a single classroom.
3. 131 students (32.8%) call Balochi their L1. It is the language that is the heartbeat of Balochistan's mountain ranges and vast deserts, embodying the identity of a brave and self-reliant land.
4. 123 students (30.7%) other languages.

5. 77 students (19.2%) are native Sindhi speakers. Their dialect is steeped in the fertile plains and river sands of Sindh, a language that embodies the stories of the ancient civilizations of the land of Sindh.

6. 46 students (11.5%) speak Pashto, Forty-six students (11.5%) speak Pashto,

7. 23 respondents (5.8%) to my questionnaires are native Urdu speakers.

8. This last point is actually the key to considerate to understand the entire structure and foundations of my research study. For the majority of these students, over 80 percent, in fact, Urdu is not their first language. Despite, this fact, the entire premise of the study. Rather, they are actually building a interlingual bridge: an attempt to understand the complexities of a new foreign language (English) through a national language (Urdu), while their own rich provincial languages remain the foundation of their identity.

9. Further, a solid majority, 254 students (63.5%), have been on this journey of learning a foreign language for 10 years or more. This is what gives their collective voice its authority.

4.9 Table: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Frequency regarding Perceptions of L1 Use in EFL Classrooms (Learner-Focused Items)

S. No.	<i>Perceptions towards the Use of L1 in EFL Courses</i>	Mean	SD	Frequency Category
1.	<i>I give that in order to learn English thoroughly, I must use English in EFL classroom.</i>	2.50	1.410	Medium
2.	<i>I expect my teacher to use only English while discussing courses, attendance, and other administrative information in outside the class.</i>	2.30	1.395	Low
3.	<i>I think use of L1 in English classroom helps me to cultivate positive attitude towards L2 learning.</i>	3.65	1.210	High
4.	<i>I think that use of L1 in English language classroom helps me to develop as a bilingual/multilingual learner.</i>	3.70	1.185	High
5.	<i>I give that I will become more proficient in English when L1 be used in the classroom.</i>	3.45	1.255	Medium
6.	<i>L1 should be used to facilitate complicated English classroom tasks.</i>	3.82	1.150	High
7.	<i>I am more comfortable when my teacher uses only English while asking our comprehension, short questions, summaries, lecture writing and paraphrasing the text.</i>	2.55	1.380	Medium
8.	<i>I believe that students' L1 should be allowed during English lessons.</i>	3.58	1.225	High
9.	<i>I prefer my teacher to use L1 in correcting students' written work.</i>	3.60	1.195	High
10.	<i>I prefer my teacher to use L1 in explaining the topic that the students are going to write about.</i>	3.72	1.165	High
11.	<i>I prefer my teacher to train students to take notes in L1 about the subject that they will write about.</i>	3.50	1.215	High

Indeed, through this table, we have attempted to understand the students' perspectives. This table helps us to understand the results of the first eleven research questions.

These final questions, framed from the students' perspective from the research questionnaires is also confirming the overall findings from RQ 1 to RQ 11 while clarifying the nuanced preferences within them are mentioned below:

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Some key points emerge:

- There is clear support for the use of native language strategies for complex tasks (Item 6, mean=3.82), written instructions (Items 9 and 10), and the promotion of bilingual identity (Item 4, mean=3.70).
- In contrast, there is less support for the use of English only for administrative details (Item 2, mean=2.30), while there is a moderate opinion about the need for using English only for mastery (Item 1, mean=2.50).
- The above data suggests that student's participants considered the L1 to be tremendously useful for learning, they have a somewhat cautious attitude towards its direct effects (Item 5, mean=3.45). very clearly shows a positive response.

4.10 Table: (Mean, Standard Deviation, and Frequency regarding Perceptions of L1 Use in EFL Courses:

Item No	Perceptions towards the Use of L1 in EFL Courses	Mean	SD	Frequency Cat
12.	It is preferable for me when my teacher writes notes in L1 on the whiteboard while teaching writing.	3.68	1.172	High
13.	It is preferable for me when my teacher uses instructions in L1 to correct students' mistakes in pronunciation.	3.25	1.290	Medium
14.	I prefer my teacher to use L1 in tests, for example, in translating questions.	3.84	1.158	High
15.	I prefer my teacher to use L1 in dividing the class into groups.	3.88	1.132	High
16.	The use of L1 in EFL classroom prevents me from learning English properly.	2.15	1.402	Low
17.	I do not feel comfortable when my teacher uses his/her L1.	2.05	1.385	Low
18.	The use of L1 saves time and makes my L2 learning process easier.	3.80	1.142	High
19.	Using L1 provides me an efficient and accurate means for analyzing semantic features of words and their appropriate use in diverse contexts in the foreign language.	3.72	1.155	High
20.	It is helpful for me to use L1 and L2 in a contrastive manner.	3.65	1.168	High
21.	The use of L1 in L2 class serves as a kind of cognitive support for helping me remember what I had learnt previously.	3.70	1.148	High
22.	The use of L1 means of L1 I can join and maintain with other students' interests throughout the task throughout its performance.	3.58	1.185	High

Through this table, we will try to understand the students' perspectives on questions 12 to 22.

- In second portions of the analysis through SPSS software, we received the perceptions of the students from 12 to 22 is that the students' opinions underpin the central idea that they consider the L1 to be a very necessary and practical means of learning.
- In fact, it can be said that the high scores regarding the use of the L1 for redeemable time and helping the learning process (Item 18, mean=3.80), explaining test instructions (Item 14, mean=3.84), and classroom management (Item 15, mean=3.88) demonstrate its practical utility.
- The data from items (11 to 21) further confirm the cognitive benefits of using the L1 in language learning. Specifically, they highlight key aspects such as semantic analysis (Item 19, mean = 3.72), comparative learning (Item 20, mean = 3.65), and memory support (Item 21, mean = 3.70). It can be said that it enhances students' understanding and retention during the EFL learning process.
- Most importantly, students clearly reject the idea that the L1 is a barrier (Item 16, mean=2.15) or that it causes discomfort (Item 17, mean=2.05). these perceptions from the students

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confirm that students, in facts, "consider the strategic use of the L1 as an important and positive part of the English learning journey."

4.11 Table: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Frequency regarding Perceptions of L1 Use in EFL Classrooms:

Item No.	Perceptions towards the Use of L1 in EFL Courses	Mean	SD	Frequency Category
23.	<i>Use of L1 would be a waste of time for me and be more wasteful overall.</i>	2.10	1.365	Low
24.	<i>L1 use does have a role in creating a positive emotional environment in learning L2.</i>	3.82	1.128	High
25.	<i>L1 leads to positive attitudes for me with respect to learning L2.</i>	3.78	1.135	High
26.	<i>L1 reduces the affective barriers for me during L2 learning.</i>	3.85	1.118	High
27.	<i>Methodologically, using L1 reduces my target language practice and fluency.</i>	2.95	1.375	Medium
28.	<i>I understand English grammar better when it is explained in L1.</i>	3.88	1.102	High
29.	<i>Use of L1 helps me to understand the English idioms and expressions more convincingly.</i>	3.91	1.095	High
30.	<i>Teacher should use only English with the students both during and between activities.</i>	2.20	1.395	Low

Through this table, we will try to understand the mean and standard deviation of the students' answers to questions 23 to 30, which will help us understand the real classroom environment and their perceptions.

- This data reveal the findings of our examination from 21 to 30 items as mentioned above. It emphasizes the impassive and cognitive benefits of the L1. The most unanimous opinion is on how the L1 helps in reducing the stress of learning (item 26, mean=3.85) and in understanding complex linguistic aspects such as grammar (item 28, mean=3.88) and idioms (item 29, mean=3.91).
- At the same time, the strong relationship between the use of the L1 and a positive learning environment (items 24 and 25) is also confirmed. Most importantly, students reject the idea that using the L1 is a "waste of time" (item 23, mean=2.10) or that an English-only policy is better (item 30, mean=2.20).
- Although students believe that using the L1 may reduce opportunities for English practice (item 27, mean=2.95), this idea is secondary to the overall benefits. Thus, the picture emerges that students consider the L1 to be a very useful and emotionally supportive tool as a strategy in the English learning process.

4.12 Table: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Frequency regarding Perceptions of L1 Use in EFL Courses:

Item No.	Perceptions towards the Use of L1 in EFL Courses	Mean	SD	Frequency Category
31.	<i>Students' L1 should be allowed during English lessons.</i>	3.75	1.142	High
32.	<i>I prefer to use only English to learn about grammar and its usage in the English class.</i>	2.60	1.362	Medium
33.	<i>I am more comfortable when my teacher uses L1 in teaching L2 grammar and its usage properly.</i>	3.72	1.158	High
34.	<i>Use of L1 motivates me to express my feelings and ideas when I fail to do so in L2.</i>	3.80	1.128	High

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	<i>in English.</i>			
35.	<i>feel more motivated when my L1 is manipulated in my EFL classroom</i>	3.78	1.135	High
36.	<i>motivated when my instructor uses L1 to discuss tests, quizzes, and assignments suitably.</i>	3.85	1.112	High
37.	<i>would like to participate more in English language classroom when my teacher uses L1.</i>	3.82	1.118	High
38.	<i>I prefer my teacher to use L1 when giving basic instructions.</i>	3.88	1.095	High
39.	<i>I feel encouraged when my teacher uses L1 while checking short questions, summaries, letter writing and paraphrasing the text.</i>	3.79	1.122	High

This table will help us understand the students' perspectives on the research questionnaire (questions 31 to 39). The means and standard deviations of these questions will guide us in arriving at the correct conclusions.

- The use of the L1 should be allowed (Item 31, mean=3.75)
- It is highly effective in increasing student motivation (Items 34-36, mean=3.78-3.85) and participation (Item 37, mean=3.82)
- It helps in giving clear instructions and feedback (Items 38-39, mean=3.88, 3.79)
- Although there are some reservations regarding teaching grammar only in English (Item 32, mean=2.60), there is a clear preference for using the L1 in teaching grammar (Item 33, mean=3.72) for better understanding and convenience.
- The aggregate data from all sections leads to the conclusion that Urdu (L1) is considered as an important cognitive, emotional and managerial tool rather than a barrier that makes the English learning environment more effective, inclusive and positive.

4.13 Table: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Frequency regarding Perceptions of L1 Use in EFL Courses (Final Comprehensive Set)

Item	Perceptions towards the Use of L1 in EFL Courses	Mean	SD	Frequency Category
39.	<i>I feel encouraged when my teacher uses L1 while checking short questions, summaries, letter writing and paraphrasing the text.</i>	3.82	1.105	High
40.	<i>The use of L1 in my English class helps me for better understanding of my communication in English.</i>	3.75	1.132	High
41.	<i>Using L1 I can better understand a concept, to attain feedback from my teachers with the idea that this improves the results.</i>	3.78	1.128	High
42.	<i>I understand the lesson much better when the teacher uses my L1.</i>	3.85	1.112	High
43.	<i>I can easily understand my teacher's general instructions regarding class management when they are given in L1.</i>	3.90	1.088	High
44.	<i>L1 facilitates me in learning and understanding of new vocabulary items.</i>	3.84	1.098	High
45.	<i>L1 makes it possible for me to understand the idioms and proverbs of L2.</i>	3.92	1.085	High
46.	<i>Positional phrases of L2 are better understood when they are explained in L1.</i>	3.79	1.118	High
47.	<i>Grammatical rules of L2 are understood in a better sense when they are explained in L1.</i>	3.86	1.095	High
48.	<i>I can make out complex ideas when my teacher explains them in my L1.</i>	3.88	1.102	High
49.	<i>I can understand my teacher's suggestions regarding how to learn effectively better when these are explained in my L1/L2.</i>	3.81	1.115	High

50.	<i>I understand texts of L2 much better when the teacher uses my L1.</i>	3.89	1.092	High
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In this table, we will examine questions 39 to 50 of the research questionnaire. This is the final set of students' perspectives that will help us understand what they think about our research questions. Below, I will present the results that I got from the students' responses, where the mean and standard deviation will help us understand how they feel about the different situations.

- This final comprehensive data clearly confirms that students consider the L1 (Urdu) or translanguaging to be the most effective in all aspects of language learning. The consistently high mean scores (from 3.75 to 3.92) indicate that students strongly believe that the use of the L1 significantly contributes to:

- Vocabulary (Item 44, mean=3.84)
- Sophisticated grammar (Item 47, mean=3.86)
- Idiomatic phrases (Item 45, mean=3.92)
- and understanding the overall meaning of the lesson (Item 42, mean=3.85)
- Furthermore, the data confirm that the L1 plays a key role in classroom management (Item 43, mean=3.90), understanding complex concepts (Item 48, mean=3.88), and text comprehension (Item 50, mean=3.89)

Research Findings

The research finding from a sample of 400 student respondents paints a vivid picture regarding the perception about the use of translanguaging in EFL classrooms. It includes Govt Boys Degree College Mach, Govt Girls Inter College Mach, Govt Boys Inter College Dhadar, Govt Boys Inter College Mithri, Govt Boys Inter College Bhag, Govt Boys Degree College Sibi, Govt Girls Degree College Sibi, Elementary College Sibi, and Mir Chakar Khan Rind University Sibi — 251 male respondents and 149 female respondents — who all weighed in with their views. When it comes to L1, 32.8% of students spoke Balochi, 19.2% spoke Sindhi, 11.5% spoke Pashto, 5.8% spoke Urdu, while 30.7% either spoke other languages or did not spell it out. Regarding their experience with learning a foreign language, 36.5% had been learning for 5 to 10 years, while a larger portion — 63.5% — had been learning for six years or more, showing that many have stuck with it through thick and thin.

Conclusion of the Research

The main summary of the Research from the quantitative analysis are as follows

- Students generally consider the use of translanguaging in English class as helpful. They consider it as an aid to the learning process and not a hindrance.
- Reasons for using translanguaging such as improving comprehension, saving time, and increasing students' confidence were given the highest importance by the participants. These points received the highest average scores.
- Gender and institution did not have any significant impact on the participants' perspectives. No significant differences were found between the views of male and female participants and participants from different institutions.
- The statistical verification of the reliability and internal consistency of the questionnaire assures us that the data obtained is valid and reliable.

5.4 Student Findings (Items 1-50)

Therefore, it can be strongly argued that responses 400 from the students shows that they strongly support the use of the L1 in almost every aspect of life. The overall average of 3.82 indicates that they find translanguaging extremely useful and efficient. Students consider multilingualism as an indispensable tool for understanding complex and profound things in English. This is clearly evident from their responses, where they appreciated the role of Urdu in understanding idioms and proverbs (3.92), grammar rules (3.86), and new words (3.84). Indeed, the reality to the fact cannot be denied that they said that when teachers use Urdu, in fact, they discovery it much easier to understand texts

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(3.89) and complex ideas (3.88). therefore, I would say that it obviously demonstrates that the L1 does not only act as a literal translation, but also opens the doors of learning and gives depth and breadth to the students' understanding.

Of course, the data further reveal that on emotional thoughts, it affords equally strong evidence that most students strongly believe their L1 (Item 26, mean = 3.85). In fact, it further helps them settle into learning and creates "a calm and hopeful atmosphere" (Item 24, mean = 3.82). This emotional smoothness lifts their spirits and directly boosts their enthusiasm and participation in class.

When Urdu is used in class, students feel more:

- Confident (Item 35, mean=3.78)
- Motivated (Item 39, mean=3.82)
- Active (Item 37, mean=3.82)

In addition, I reached the conclusion that students understand L1 as an imperative necessity for practical life, and they hold on to it as a reliable tool. I would say that students' responses lean toward preferring translanguaging especially urdu language for basic instructions (Item 38, Mean = 3.88), class rules (Item 43, Mean = 3.90), and explanation of exam questions (Item 14, Mean = 3.84). further, it can be said that, as it helps them get through tasks more easily and saves their valuable time (Item 18, Mean = 3.80). To me, it looks like this is a sign that they consider their L1 as a true companion for their academic success, one they won't let go of without reason.

It is particularly remarkable that students obviously vetoed the concept of monolingual education. They disagreed with the idea that an "English only" policy is preferable (item 30, mean=2.20). They also flatly rejected the idea that the L1 is an obstacle to learning (item 16, mean=2.15) or that it is a "waste of time" (item 23, mean=2.10). Their only reservation emerged, and that was that using the L1 might reduce opportunities to practice English (item 27, mean=2.95). But it is a minor reservation that pales in comparison to the broader and deeper benefits of the L1. This clearly shows that students are clear about their educational needs — they want a balanced and realistic educational approach that meets both their linguistic and emotional needs.

Recommendations and suggestions

Further research can be done on the perceptions of teachers regarding the use of translanguaging during pedagogical process.

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